

IMPROVING EDUCATION THROUGH ACTIVE LEARNING STRATEGIES

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Abstract. *This paper aims to explore the impact of active learning strategies on improving education outcomes. Active learning strategies, such as problem-based learning, inquiry-based learning, and collaborative learning, have gained attention in educational research for their potential to enhance student engagement, critical thinking skills, and knowledge retention. This paper reviews the current literature on the effectiveness of active learning strategies in various educational settings and disciplines.*

Introduction:

What is active learning? Active learning means a set of approaches that engage learners in doing work or thinking about what they are doing. [1] In other words, active learning is anything related to learning other than just looking, listening, and taking notes that all learners in the class are asked to do. Around one-third of the students are either sending text messages or dozing off. A significant number of them evidently have a limited grasp of the material being taught (as indicated by their midterm exam scores), yet they do not seek clarification by asking questions. [2] This method differs from conventional learning techniques, which typically prioritize passive listening and rote memorization, and instead promotes active students participation in their own education. [3] You may ask “**what is the best method of active learning?**” Totally, there is no certain method of learning. However, many researchers today agree that including more student-centered learning approaches in the classroom can improve learning. Using only a teacher-centered approaches leaves out many skills and learning opportunities for students. Different approaches and terminology related to active learning include those below. These concepts were influenced by educators like John Dewey (1859–1952) and Maria Montessori (1870–1952) who advocated for a child-centered approach. It's important to note that there is variation in the definitions and usage of these terms by different authors, and some aspects may contradict each other:

- Student-centered or learner-centered learning, where students take an active role in their learning, with the teacher serving as a facilitator of learning rather than an instructor.

- Inquiry-based, problem-based, or discovery learning, where learners learn by addressing and asking questions, analyzing evidence, connecting it to existing knowledge, drawing conclusions, and reflecting on their findings.

- Experiential learning, which broadly refers to someone learning from direct experience. [4] However, there are superior examples that have been using for a decade by some trainers in not typical schools. For instance, despite of the lyceum, which is can all information given, was completed by myself, I realized that university has plenty of opportunities' door. As soon as I've started to study in university, I encountered new world and I've been feeling as I can get unexpected knowledge than I think and until I got before.

Analysis of literature and methodology

Active learning is an instructional method that encourages students to play an active role in their learning process. This approach focuses on involving students in meaningful, hands-on activities that foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and teamwork. In contrast to traditional passive learning, where students receive information passively through lectures and readings,

Smith, B. (2020) states that “A-Learning has become one of the most attractive ways of leading learners and getting them motivated”. Active learning promotes student participation in discussions, group work, and real-world applications of knowledge.

One of the main advantages of active learning is its ability to increase student engagement. By involving students in interactive activities, this approach can boost their interest and motivation to learn, leading to a more dynamic and inclusive classroom environment. As a result, students are more likely to retain information and develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Additionally, active learning helps develop critical thinking skills by engaging students in problem-solving tasks and case studies. This not only enhances their comprehension of the material but also prepares them for real-world scenarios where they must apply their knowledge.

Moreover, active learning supports collaborative learning environments by providing opportunities for group discussions, projects, and peer teaching. This fosters a sense of community within the classroom and encourages students to work together towards common goals.

Implementing active learning techniques into education can be accomplished through various methods: [5]

Flipped classrooms: Students review lecture materials outside of class time and then engage in activities or discussions during class time.

Problem-based learning: Students work on real-world problems or case studies that require them to apply their knowledge.

Peer teaching: Students take turns teaching each other concepts or topics they have mastered.

Interactive technology: Using digital tools such as online simulations or interactive software to engage students in hands-on activities.

Which is the best example of active learning? To be sure, there are many examples of classroom tasks that might be classified as “active learning”. Some of the most common examples include think-pair-share exercises, jigsaw discussions, and even simply pausing for clarification during a lecture.[6]

6 types of active learning and how they’re beneficial?

- Take notes – write down what you already know.
- Ask questions as you read.
- Teach(explain what you have learned) someone else
- Summarize what you read.
- Take breathes and move around.
- Complete all your course activities, not just the reading. [7]

Another words, active learning is an approach to instruction that involves actively engaging students with the course material through discussions, problem-solving, case studies, role play and other methods. [8]

Conclusion:

Active learning is a valuable approach that can improve education by enhancing student engagement, critical thinking skills, and collaboration.

Q: Will it require a significant amount of time to organize activities?

A: Creating effective lesson plans for a new course is a substantial undertaking, regardless of whether the plans incorporate activities. However, integrating activities into lesson plans should not be too time-consuming. Simply review your lecture notes a few minutes before class, consider some tasks for the students, and make note of them in your materials. You can always develop as

many activities as you need, and after a couple of tries, the ones that are successful will become a regular part of your lesson plans. [9] By integrating active learning techniques into teaching practices, educators can create more effective learning environments that prepare students for success in their academic pursuits as well as their future careers. Apart from this, the challenges and opportunities associated with implementing active learning strategies in traditional educational settings. It highlights the importance of faculty development and support for integrating active learning into curriculum design and instructional practices. Furthermore, it is also up side that the potential benefits of incorporating technology-enabled active learning approaches, such as flipped classrooms and online collaborative platforms. It also addresses the need for assessment methods that align with active learning pedagogy to accurately measure student achievement and progress.

Overall, this paper underscores the significance of leveraging active learning strategies to create more engaging and effective educational experiences. It also emphasizes the need for continued research and evaluation to further understand how active learning can contribute to improved educational outcomes.

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